

SHEAR AND BENDING PROPERTIES OF CERAMIC FIBER REINFORCED SILICA AEROGEL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Aerogel matrix composites, Anisotropy, Failure modes, Mechanical Properties, Notches

ABSTRACT

Aerogel has been used as excellent thermal insulation material because of its extremely low thermal conductivity. However, its poor mechanical properties such as low strength and high brittleness greatly limit its applications in aerospace and building structures. By adding reinforced materials, aerogel matrix composites with higher strength and better toughness can be prepared without sacrificing major thermal insulation performance. Ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites are prepared by impregnating ceramic fibers with aerogel precursor and then dried in supercritical condition. Recently, mechanical properties of aerogel matrix composites have been investigated increasingly, but the material property anisotropy has not been referred. It is important to obtain the comprehensive knowledge of thermal and mechanical properties in some load-bearing engineering structures.

Shear and bending tests were conducted on the ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites at room temperature according to ASTM standards. The effects of material orientations on mechanical properties and failure modes were analyzed, as well as the different damage mechanisms and failure modes of in-plane shear specimens with or without notches. Results show that the composites have anisotropic mechanical properties. The shear modulus and ultimate strength of in-plane shear specimens are about 3 times and 8 times those of interlaminar shear specimens. Meanwhile, the special ply feature of ceramic fibers results in the differences of shear failure modes and mechanisms. Under in-plane shear load, cracks in V-notched specimens initiate from the notches and propagate along the path between two notches, which is obviously distinct from specimens without notches. The bending modulus and ultimate strength of in-plane bending specimens are both slightly higher than those of out-of-plane bending specimens. The load-bearing ability of out-of-plane bending specimens after reaching the ultimate stress decreases more slowly due to different failure modes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aerogels comprised of nano-sized particles linking as an open-pore structure are prepared by a sol-gel process followed by supercritical drying technology [1, 2]. They have been applied in various fields since the first preparation by Kistler [3] in 1931. Among these potential applications, thermal insulation is the most significant field because aerogels are solid materials with porosities from about 80% to 99.8% and have the lowest thermal conductivities. A record low conductivity of 0.012W/(m·K) at 300K and 0.1MPa was reported recently for monolithic organic aerogels [4, 5].

However, the low strength and high brittleness restrict their applications. Efforts have been made to produce fiber or particle reinforced aerogel matrix composites with higher strength [6-8]. Recently, mechanical properties of aerogel matrix composites have been investigated. Gao [9] found a great

increase in mechanical properties of ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites. Meanwhile, the research showed that the strength of the aerogel matrix composites increased first and then decreased with the increase of fiber volume fraction, while increased with the increase of matrix density. Rosa-Fox [10] investigated the compression and creep behaviors of hybrid organic-inorganic aerogels at room temperature. It was been found that the modulus was lower than the pure silica aerogel during the elastic stage, but higher during the rupture stage. Compression tests at high temperature were conducted by Shi [11] to investigate the anisotropic mechanical characteristic. In-plane modulus increased with increasing temperature, but out-of-plane modulus decreased with increasing temperature. Roy [12] characterized the mechanical behaviors of isocyanate-crosslinked silica aerogel by approach of compression, three-point bending and dynamic mechanical analysis tests. Three-dimensional distinct-element analysis simulations were also performed to understand the structure-property relationship. A new multi-scale model was proposed by Lu [13] to investigate the relationship between the mechanical properties and microstructure of fiber reinforced silica aerogel composites. Results showed that the fiber characteristics including the fiber volume fraction, length and curvature were significant for the mechanical properties of the composites.

With the urgent demand in engineering applications, research on the mechanical properties of aerogel matrix composites is more and more important. Ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites are excellent load-bearing insulation materials, which have superior thermal insulation performance and relatively higher strength. It is necessary for us to have an overall knowledge of the mechanical properties of the composites. In this paper, shear and bending tests were conducted at room temperature according to ASTM standards. The effects of material orientation on mechanical properties and failure modes were analyzed, as well as the different damage and failure modes of in-plane shear specimens with or without notches.

2 MATERIALS

Ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites were prepared by sol-gel process and supercritical drying technology [6]. SiO_2 sol was prepared by a two-step acid-base procedure. First, tetraethoxysilane (TEOS), the precursor for aerogel, was mixed with ethanol (ETOH). Then a mixture of hydrochloride (HCL), water (H_2O) and ETOH was added to the solution. After sufficient hydrolysis of TEOS by acid catalysis, ammonium hydroxide ($\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), H_2O and ETOH were added into the solution for base catalysis, until the SiO_2 sol was finally produced. The molar ratio of TEOS: HCL: $\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: H_2O is about 1: 1.8×10^{-3} : 3.6×10^{-3} : 4 [14].

Then inorganic ceramic fibers were added into the gel. The fibers with average diameter of 4~5 μm are about 30~40mm long and mainly composed of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 . With the continuous aging of the mixture of SiO_2 gel and ceramic fibers, the frameworks of the composites were gradually formed. Further, supercritical drying was conducted with ETOH as medium at 516K and 6.3MPa to eventually obtain the ceramic fiber reinforced aerogel matrix composites.

The density of test materials by the above method is about 0.29g/cm³. The volume percentage of reinforcing fibers is about 7%. These fibers are mainly arranged in the in-plane direction (X and Y) shown in Fig. 1, while few fibers are distributed in the out-of-plane direction (Z).

Figure 1: Ceramic fiber reinforced aerogel matrix composites (a) structure schematic; (b) fiber distribution in XOY plane

3 EXPERIMENT

Experiment scheme was made referring to ASTM standards. Shear and bending tests were conducted on an Electronic Universal Test Machine WDW3020, in which the controlled variation of force within 1% and displacement within 0.001mm. During these tests, displacement loading rate 1mm/min was used.

3.1 Shear test

In-plane and interlaminar shear tests were conducted according to ASTM D 7078 [15] and D 4255 [16], as shown in Fig. 2. The dimensions of shear specimens are shown in Table 1. The notch dimensions of in-plane shear V-notched specimen are: width=12.7mm, depth=12.7mm, notch angle=90°. The shear stress τ is calculated by dividing the load P by the effective area A . In the in-plane shear tests, the shear strain γ is calculated by dividing the displacement δ by the distance between two grips b , which is only suitable for the specimen without notches. In the interlaminar shear tests, the shear strain γ is calculated by dividing the displacement δ by the specimen thickness t .

Figure 2: Shear test methods and fixtures (a) in-plane shear; (b) interlaminar shear

Test	Number	Type	Dimension mm×mm×mm	Note
Shear	S1-1	Interlaminar	L×W×t 80×60×14	
	S1-2	Interlaminar	80×60×14	
	S1-3	Interlaminar	80×60×14	
	S2-1	In-plane	114×69.9×14	
	S2-2	In-plane	114×69.9×14	V-notched
Bending	B1-1	In-plane	L×W×h 90×15×5	
	B1-2	In-plane	90×15×5	
	B2-1	Out-of-plane	90×14×5	
	B2-2	Out-of-plane	90×14×5	

Table 1: Mechanical property test scheme and specimen dimensions

3.2 Bending test

Bending tests were conducted according to ASTM C 1341 [17]. The dimensions of bending specimens are shown in Table 1. According to the different directions of bending moment applied to bending specimens, bending tests in this study were divided into two types: in-plane bending and out-of-plane bending. Fig. 3 presents the test device of three-point bending tests. The length of the loading span S is 80mm. The bending stress σ and strain ϵ are calculated by the following equations:

$$\sigma = \frac{3P \cdot S}{2W \cdot h^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{6\delta \cdot h}{L^2} \quad (2)$$

The equivalent bending modulus E_b is obtained by fitting the bending stress-strain curve in order to evaluate the material toughness in this paper.

Figure 3: Three-point bending test

Figure 4: Shear stress-strain curves (a) interlaminar shear; (b) in-plane shear

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Shear property

Fig. 4(a) shows the interlaminar shear stress-strain curves of ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites, while Fig. 4(b) shows the in-plane shear stress-strain curve of the specimen without notches. There are some differences between the interlaminar and in-plane shear behaviors. Before the load reached the ultimate stress, the two types of shear curves both showed the linear feature basically. Once the ultimate level was reached, the interlaminar shear stress abruptly declined to a level close to zero, while the in-plane shear stress decreased gradually.

Because ceramic fibers are mainly arranged in the in-plane direction, the composites have the special layer feature, which results in different shear failure modes and mechanisms. There were few reinforcing fibers through the interfaces between fiber layers in the interlaminar shear specimens. The silica aerogel matrix was the main load-bearing part during the interlaminar shear loading. These interfaces had the worse strength and cracks initiated and quickly propagated at some interfaces close to the loading axis. As shown in Fig. 5(a), this caused that the composites fractured in a quite large area and lost the load-bearing ability. On the other hand, the reinforcing fibers were the main load-bearing part during the in-plane shear loading. The fiber pull-outs and fracture could absorb energy

continually so that the composites could not promptly lose the load-bearing ability once cracks initiated. As can be seen in Fig. 5(b), cracks propagated along the loading axis in each fiber layer in the in-plane shear tests. These crack growth paths deflected due to the block of the fibers, so the fracture appearance presented those irregular shapes in Fig. 5(b).

Figure 5: Failure modes of shear specimens (a) interlaminar shear; (b) in-plane shear

Figure 6: Failure modes of in-plane V-notched shear specimen

Under the in-plane shear load, the failure modes of the specimens with and without notches were inconsistent. Because of the local stress concentration, the cracks initiated near the clamped position of the specimen without notches. It was obviously different in the V-notched specimen, as shown in Fig. 6. The cracks initiated near the notch tips and propagated along the path between the two notches. This was because the nominal shear stress was the highest between the notches.

Table 2 presents the shear properties from various types of shear tests. According to the results, the ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites have the directional shear properties. The in-plane shear modulus and ultimate stress are respectively about 3 times and 8 times the interlaminar shear modulus and ultimate stress.

Test type	Number	Shear modulus G/MPa	Ultimate stress τ_u/MPa	Ultimate strain $\varepsilon_u/(\text{mm}/\text{mm})$
Interlaminar	S1-1	3.22	0.112	0.0362
Interlaminar	S1-2	2.94	0.103	0.0356
Interlaminar	S1-3	2.98	0.094	0.0318
In-plane	S2-1	10.44	0.824	0.0855
In-plane	S2-2	–	0.951	–

Table 2: Shear properties of ceramic fiber reinforced aerogel matrix composites

4.2 Bending property

Fig. 7(a) and Fig. 7(b) respectively show the in-plane and out-of-plane bending stress-strain curves of ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites. The basic features of two types of curves are similar. These curves kept linear basically before the load level reached the ultimate stress. Once the ultimate level was reached, the decline of in-plane bending curves was faster than that of out-of-plane bending curves. It could be seen that the composites were easier to fracture under in-plane bending load according to the material orientation. Table 3 presents the bending properties from various types of in-plane and out-of-plane tests. Like the shear properties, the ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites also have the directional bending properties. The bending modulus and ultimate stress of in-plane bending specimens are both slightly higher than those of out-of-plane bending specimens.

As discussed in the section 4.1, bending failure modes and mechanisms were also related to the layer feature of the composites. Under the in-plane bending load, the upper fiber layers were in compression while the lower were in tension. Each fiber layer in tension failed when the stress in this layer reached the peak. In addition, the interfaces between layers were weak and unable to withstand the shear effect under three-point bending load. Therefore, in-plane bending specimens were easier to fail and had the failure appearance shown in Fig. 8.

The direction of bending moment was perpendicular to the fiber layers in the out-of-plane bending tests. Besides the fiber pull-outs and fracture, the crack deflection in the fiber layers due to the block of the fibers was also one kind of important damage mechanism. Thus, it would consume more time that the out-of-plane bending stress decreased to the same level compared with the in-plane bending. In addition, there were some cracks along the length direction of out-of-bending specimens in Fig. 9(b), which was because some interfaces between layers were quite weak and the debonding happened.

Figure 7: Bending stress-strain curves (a) in-plane bending; (b) out-of-plane bending

Figure 8: In-plane bending failure modes (a) upper surface; (b) lower surface

Figure 9: Out-of-bending bending failure modes (a) upper surface; (b) lower surface

Test type	Number	Bending modulus	Ultimate stress	Ultimate strain
		E_{eq}/MPa	τ_u/MPa	$\varepsilon_u/(\text{mm/mm})$
In-plane	B1-1	438.97	2.63	0.0064
In-plane	B1-2	467.03	2.87	0.0063
Out-of-plane	B2-1	406.93	2.07	0.0065
Out-of-plane	B2-2	376.54	2.24	0.0081

Table 3: Bending properties of ceramic fiber reinforced aerogel matrix composites

5 CONCLUSIONS

Ceramic fiber reinforced silica aerogel matrix composites have anisotropic mechanical properties. The modulus and strength of in-plane shear are approximately 3 times and 8 times those of interlaminar shear. The modulus and strength of in-plane bending are both slightly higher than those of out-of-plane bending. Shear and bending failure modes and mechanisms are related to the layer feature of the composites. Different material orientations may result in the differences of fracture appearances under the same loading form. Besides the fiber pull-outs and fracture, the crack deflection in the fiber layers due to the block of the fibers was also an important damage mechanism.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was supported by the National Basic Research Program of China (No. 2015CB057400) and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NO. 51275023).

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